

On the occurrence of *Isomira thoracica* (FABRICIUS, 1792) in Poland

Występowanie *Isomira thoracica* (FABRICIUS, 1792) w Polsce

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ABSTRACT: Specimens of *Isomira* MULSANT, 1856 from various regions of Poland were examined. All specimens are identified as *Isomira thoracica* (FABRICIUS, 1792). The complex history of identification of the *Isomira* species from Poland is briefly discussed. It is concluded that specimens identified by Polish authors as *Isomira murina* (LINNAEUS, 1758) belong in fact to *I. thoracica*. There is a need to revise the entomological collections and verify previous identifications.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Tenebrionidae, Alleculinae, *Isomira*, Poland.

Introduction

The genus *Isomira* MULSANT, 1856 inhabits almost the whole world except the Australasian and Neotropical Realms. In Palaearctic, it contains 78 species of which 10 are distributed in Central Europe (NOVÁK 2014). Because of the very uniform external morphology, the classification and taxonomy of that taxon is still insufficiently recognized. Beetles from the genus *Isomira* are associated with grasslands and xerothermic environments, and its larvae feed in the soil between the roots of grasses, herbaceous and perennial plants.

The number of *Isomira* species recognized from the territory of Poland is uncertain. BURAKOWSKI in his key for identification of Polish Alleculinae (1976) described and illustrated two species belonging to Polish fauna: *I. murina* (LINNAEUS, 1758) and *I. semiflava* (KÜSTER, 1852). In 1973, SZYMCZAKOWSKI identified the third species, *I. icteropa* (KÜSTER, 1852), collected from the region of Małopolska, which was subsequently recorded by KLASIŃSKI (2007) from Sokole Góry near Częstochowa. All three species were listed in the Catalogue of Polish Fauna by BURAKOWSKI et al. (1987). NOVÁK & PETERSSON (2008) in the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, listed only two species from Poland: *I. murina* (= *I. semiflava*) and *I. icteropa*. However, NOVÁK (2014) recognized *I. semiflava* as a separate species and mentioned that it inhabits Poland, probably after BURAKOWSKI (1987). In the newest catalogue of Tenebrionidae of Poland (IWAN et al.

2012), the authors recognized just one valid species occurring in Poland, *I. murina*. They treat *I. semiflava* as a synonym of *I. murina*, and *I. icteropa* as incorrect identification of female specimens recorded by the previous authors.

The problem with the correct identification of the *Isomira* species in Europe lasts much longer and is nested deeper in time. The major problem concerns the distinction between the *I. murina* and *I. thoracica* (FABRICIUS, 1792), which were either recognized as independent species (FABRICIUS 1792), or as synonyms (SEIDLITZ 1896, WEISE 1974). Polish (BURAKOWSKI 1976) and Russian (DUBROVINA 1982) entomologists followed the opinion of WEISE (1974), they treated *I. thoracica* as a colour variation of *I. murina*, and confirmed that *I. murina* inhabits Central and Eastern Europe. However, BOUYON (2002) re-examined the type series of both taxa and found out that they are separate species, with well-defined differences in male copulatory organs. He concluded that *I. murina* occurs in Western Europe, while only *I. thoracica* is present in Central and Eastern Europe.

Material

To verify the correct identification of *Isomira* species inhabiting Poland, the following material was examined (coll. KS – K. SZAWARYN collection, coll. RR – R. RUTA collection):

- Baltic Coast: CF52/CF62 Gdańsk, Wyspa Sobieszewska, 11-17 VI 2017,3 exx., 10-16 VI 2018, 2♂2♀, leg. K. SZAWARYN (coll. KS).

- Masurian Lake District: DE85 Wardąg lake, 22 VI 2020, 1♂2♀, vegetation on the lake shore, leg. D. MARCZAK (coll. KS).
- Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: XU18 Piła vic., 17 VI 1999, 1♂, young forest near Piaszczyste lake, leg. R. RUTA (coll. RR); XU38 hill ad Byszewice, 31 V 2002, 1♂, leg. R. RUTA (coll. RR); XU05 Pianówka near Czarnków, 26 V 2007, 1♂, xerothermic grassland, leg. R. RUTA (coll. RR).
- Mazovian Lowland: DC98 Warszawa, Lasek na Kole 26 VI 2020 1 ex., T. CZERWIŃSKI (coll. KS); DD80 Łomna Las, 17 VI 2020 1♂5♀, leg. T. CZERWIŃSKI (coll. KS).
- Małopolska Upland: DA69 Skowronno, 25 V 1983, 2♂, leg. L. BOROWIEC (coll. RR).

- Lublin Upland: GB03 Gródek near Hrubieszów, 27 V 1994, 2♂, leg. L. BOROWIEC (coll. RR).
- Roztocze: FB30 Lipowiec, 14 VI 1989, 1♂ ex., leg. L. BOROWIEC; FB54 Tarnogóra near Izbica, 15 VI 1989, 2♂, leg. L. BOROWIEC (coll. RR).
- Eastern Sudeten Mts: WS33 Szklarska Poręba Śr., 16-24 VI 1995, 1♂, leg. L. BOROWIEC (coll. RR).

The specimens were dissected and identified using BOUYON (2002), and NOVÁK (2014).

Results and discussion

After examination of male (Fig. 1A-D) and female (Fig. 1E) genitalia, all specimens were identified as *Isomira thoracica* (FABRICIUS, 1792). Specimen from Byszewice was previously published by RUTA (2007) as *I. murina*.

Fig. 1. *Isomira thoracica* (Fabricius, 1792): A, B – aedeagus, C – abdominal sternite IX, D – male abdominal sternite VIII, E – female abdominal sternite VIII, F – habitus, G – head and pronotum.

Ryc. 1. *Isomira thoracica* (Fabricius, 1792): A, B – aparat kopulacyjny samca, C – sternit IX odwłoka samca, D – sternit VIII odwłoka samca, E – sternit VIII odwłoko samicy, F – pokrój ciała, G – głowa i przedplecze.

Analysed specimens showed a broad variation of colour forms, from specimens that are entirely pale brown, through specimens pale brown with only head black (Fig. 1F, G), those with black head, dark brown pronotum and pale brown elytra, to specimens entirely dark gray. According to FABRICIUS (1792) and BOUYON (2002) the type specimen has reddish brown pronotum. Such variability is also typical for other species of the genus *Isomira*, which makes the colouration quite useless for identification. The only reliable character is the structure of the male genitalia, and sometimes the shape of the female sternite VIII is also useful.

Up to date, *Isomira thoracica* has been recorded in Central Europe from Czechia, Germany, Slovakia, and Hungary (NOVÁK & PETERSSON 2008). Based on the drawings of male genitalia in DUBROVINA (1982), it should also be present in Russia. However, the exact distribution of that species in Europe is difficult to estimate as for a long time specimens of *Isomira* collected from this region were identified as *I. murina*. Concerning Polish fauna, it is likely that all records previously identified as *I. murina* belong to *I. thoracica*. Therefore, there is a need to re-examine previously collected specimens of *Isomira* housed in numerous Polish collections.

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PODSUMOWANIE

Liczba gatunków z rodzaju *Isomira* MULS. występujących na terenie Polski nie jest jasna. Różni autorzy wykazywali od jednego do trzech gatunków. Dodatkowo istniały sporne poglądy odnośnie statusu *I. thoracica* F. jako osobnego gatunku lub formy barwnej *I. murina* L. Ostatnie badania BOUYON (2002) potwierdzają osobny status gatunkowy *I. thoracica*. Celem weryfikacji krajowych gatunków *Isomira* przeanalizowano chrząszcze pozyskane z kilku rejonów Polski. Stwierdzono, że wszystkie okazy należą do gatunku *I. thoracica*. Badania sugerują, że polskie okazy *Isomira* dotychczas uznawane za *I. murina* w rzeczywistości są przedstawicielami *I. thoracica*. Aby potwierdzić tą hipotezę konieczna jest dalsza weryfikacja materiałów zgromadzonych w krajowych kolekcjach zarówno historycznych, jak i współczesnych.

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